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Stability and Collapse Analysis of Terrestrial Lava Tubes under Irregular Shapes: Case Study of Skull and Valentine Caves

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Key Points:

- First numerical study of lava tube stability and collapse geometry using real data.
- Irregular cross-section geometry significantly impacts cave stability.
- Rock roof thickness variations can have minimal or significant effects on stability, depending on collapse mechanisms.

Abstract: Lava tubes have attracted increasing attention from scientists and space industry professionals due to their potential as protective shelters on planetary bodies like the Moon or Mars, as well as for scientific research. This interest has started investigations into terrestrial lava tubes as analogs for extraterrestrial caves. In this study, we present the first comprehensive numerical analysis of the stability and collapse geometry of two real lava tubes, Skull Cave and Valentine Cave, using laser scan data of their interiors and surrounding terrain. Our methodology is based on finite element limit analysis, which can accurately and efficiently replicate the natural, irregular shapes of these caves for stability analysis. We performed additional analyses by varying rock roof thickness and other parameters to validate whether previous findings from studies on artificially generated irregular shapes hold true for actual cave geometries. Our results provide new insights into how natural irregularities in cave geometry influence stability and collapse mechanisms. The results confirm the significant impact of these irregularities and offer a robust approach for assessing cave stability.

Keywords: lava tube, stability, collapse analysis, lava tube exploration, extraterrestrial caves

Plain language summary: Scientists and space experts are interested in lava tubes because they could serve as shelters on the Moon or Mars and help with research. This has led to studies of lava tubes on Earth as models for space caves. In this study, we analyzed the stability and collapse patterns of two real lava tubes, Skull Cave and Valentine Cave, using laser scans of their interiors and surroundings. We used a method called finite element limit analysis, which

accurately models the caves' irregular shapes. We also tested different rock roof thicknesses to see if past studies on artificial cave shapes apply to real ones. Our findings show how natural irregularities affect cave stability and collapse. They confirm that these irregularities play a significant role and provide a strong method for evaluating cave stability.

1. Introduction

Terrestrial lava tubes have recently attracted major attention of planetary geologists as they serve as analogs to their extraterrestrial counterparts identified on the Moon and Mars (e.g., Sauro et al., 2020). Extraterrestrial caves are considered promising targets of scientific research, exploration, and potentially suitable locations for human and robotic lunar bases in the coming decades (e.g., Titus et al., 2021, Wynne et al., 2022, *Origins, Worlds, and Life: a Decadal Strategy for Planetary Science and Astrobiology 2023–2032*, 2022, She et al., 2025). However, due to the lack of knowledge about extraterrestrial lava tubes, intensive studies of terrestrial caves are ongoing to better understand their nature, the risks related to operating inside them, and how to explore their interiors with robotic equipment (e.g., Schreiber et al., 2020, Petráček et al., 2021, Tomasi et al., 2022, Whelley et al., 2024). Currently, terrestrial lava tubes are the only reliable source of knowledge about these geological formations, despite interesting attempts to use comparative planetology to describe their geometrical features from a more general perspective (Sauro et al., 2020). It is also a motivation for the creation of databases of terrestrial lava tube shapes (e.g., Romio et al., 2025). A better understanding of the processes that form lava tubes, effusion rates, and lava rheology will also provide important knowledge to estimate environmentally significant characteristics of past volcanic eruptions. Lava tubes have been examined in a variety of ways, such as magnetometry (e.g., Bell et al., 2022), ground-penetrating radar (e.g., Esmaeile et al., (2020), laser scanning, etc. In this regard, the recent discovery of a potential cave conduit beneath the Mare Tranquillitatis Pit (Carrer et al., 2024) will further accelerate interest in lava tubes and the analysis of their collapses.

Interest in rock mass stability around underground structures arose with mining and underground construction. Empirical hypotheses, based on observations of rock-support interactions, led to theories like the arching effect, where a destressed zone above an excavation influences load distribution. Many empirical methods, such as those by Terzaghi (1943) and Airey (1974), correlate stability with geotechnical parameters. However, due to their empirical nature, these methods have limited modern applicability, as each underground structure faces unique geological conditions. Empirical methods for calculating the destressed zone in underground structures consider basic geometric parameters like height and width, making them suitable for regular anthropogenic shapes. However, natural structures, such as volcanic or karst formations, have complex geometries requiring advanced approaches. Numerical methods, like finite element method (FEM) and finite difference method (FDM), are now used to account for these complexities (e.g., Jin et al., 2018; Kong et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2018). Laser scanning enables precise mapping of complex geometries and is widely used in mining and underground construction. Researchers are refining its use to enhance numerical modeling of rock mass behavior (Janus & Ostrogórski, 2022; Monsalve et al., 2018; Bodlak, 2024, Bodlak and Izydorski, 2024). These applications are also being adopted for mapping cave shapes (e.g., Whelley et al., 2021), enabling more accurate stability analyses when combined with modern numerical methods.

Few studies assess the stability of irregular-shaped lava tubes (e.g., Chwała et al., 2024a, Chwała et al., 2024b, Whelley et al., 2024), and no standardized approach exists for such analyses, making stability assessment difficult. The scientific community suggests that studying terrestrial caves can prepare us for extraterrestrial cave exploration. A recent study on the impact of irregular lava tube shapes under lunar gravity conditions shows that such shapes can significantly affect stability and collapse geometry. However, these observations were based on artificially generated cross-sections with rough estimates from several near-circular cross-sections of La Corona Lava Tube (Tomasi et al., 2022). For this reason, in this study we propose an approach for stability assessment of lava tubes based on laser scans, which

allows to investigate direct influence of irregular cave shapes. Additionally, we have analyzed the geometric characteristics of collapses resulting from numerical analyses. For the numerical analyses, we used the upper bound theorem of limit analysis, which is implemented within OptumG2 software. The method has proven its robustness in analyzing the stability of various geotechnical and geological formations (e.g., Krabbenhoft and Lyamin, 2015; Lim et al., 2017; Chwała, 2024b). This study is the first comprehensive attempt to assess the stability of terrestrial lava tubes and analyze their variations along the lava tube path, which result from irregular geometry and irregular surface topography. The proposed approach is demonstrated on two lava tube sections, i.e., Skull Cave and Valentine Cave (Whelley et al., 2021). To make the conclusions more general, we considered several scenarios of roof geometry and rock mass mechanical properties. For example, we examined cases with horizontal surface topography and constant roof thickness for each cross-section to compare the influence of shape variability. We expect that the presented methodology for analyzing linear voids with irregular shapes will support stability analyses conducted on different objects by other researchers, and that the conclusions will further improve our understanding of the effects of irregular geometry on stability and collapses.

We have identified several types of collapses characteristic of natural cross-sections. Notably, the detected collapses are asymmetrical due to irregular geometry. It turns out that irregular geometry can significantly impact stability assessment; for example, some cross-sections with the same roof thickness exhibit lower stability despite having smaller dimensions compared to other cave sections. This highlights the importance of the chosen research direction and the need for its further development.

2. Brief description of geology of Skull Cave and Valentine Cave

The lava tubes studied in this paper are in northern California within flows related to the Medicine Lake Volcano (MLV) and within Lava Beds National Monument (LBNM). The region forms a broad highland, defined by $>2,000 \text{ km}^3$ of lava flows which are compositionally diverse, from rhyolite to basalt (Donnelly-Nolan, 2010). The eruptive history of MLV span much of the past 500,000 years.

Skull Cave is a large diameter ($\sim 18\text{--}20 \text{ m}$), multi-level lava tube which includes meter scale collapsed ceiling and wall blocks (Arnold, 1986; Larson & Larson, 1990, Bell et al., 2022). Skull cave is an evacuated segment of the Modoc Crater lava tube network, a system of lava tubes within the $36 \pm 16 \text{ ka}$ (using $40\text{Ar}/39\text{Ar}$) Modoc Crater lava flow (Donnelly-Nolan, 2010). Bell et al. (2022) identified a magnetic anomaly associated with Skull cave and other segments of the Modoc Crater lava tube network, demonstrating magnetometry as a useful tool in lava tube detection. Additional geophysics work is underway in this location (e.g., McCall et al., 2022) to refine tube detection methods, and the collapse timing of the Modoc Crater tubes (Whelley et al., 2024).

Valentine Cave is a 1-3 m diameter meandering and branching tube (e.g., Esmaeili et al., 2020). This tube is within a $\sim 12 \text{ ka}$ (radiocarbon and paleomagnetic direction) lava flow: The Valentine Cave Basalt (Donnelly-Nolan, 2010). This is a basaltic to basaltic-andesite lava that erupted from Tickner Chimineas on the flank on Medicine Lake Volcano. The ceiling of Valentine cave is fractured but largely in place and the floor is mostly composed of ropy lava (pahoehoe, Waters et al., 1990) with minor sections of rubbly-pahoehoe. Esmaeile et al., (2020) demonstrated that Skull and Valentine caves produce unique ground penetrating radar (GPR) signatures. Their methods were able to detect both the ceiling and floors of some tube segments using GPR. In this study, we analyzed the stability and collapses of both caves, motivated by the significant differences between them.

3. Cross-section preparation

In this study we used point clouds obtained by laser scanning of both cave interiors (Esmaeili et al., 2020; Whelley et al., 2021; Bell et al., 2022). For both caves, the interior cave geometry and the surface topography were available, which allows to consider actual surface topography. Spatial data in the form of point clouds (file format .las) underwent preliminary processing in the open-source software CloudCompare (CloudCompare, 2024). This preprocessing involved trimming and filtering stray and duplicate points. The primary task, however, was generating cross-sections perpendicular to the cave path, which is important for using 2D numerical modelling aimed in this study. Results of this process were closed polylines that reflect the cave geometry. The surface topography was represented by open polylines determined in the same cutting planes as cave cross-sections. Cross-section generation was made possible by built-in functions in CloudCompare, the procedure starts with defining a polyline along the cave path and defining the distance between the cross-sections. Due to the complexity of the caves geometry and the quality of measurement data, we have set a step of 1.0 m between successive cross-sections. After that, the parameters of cross-section thickness and maximum edge length are set, which were adjusted based on the complexity of the geometry and the quality of the point cloud for a given cave fragment. The final step in constructing the cross-sections was exporting them to graphic files with format (.dxf) and text files with format (.poly). Text format was used as source for MATLAB based procedures that creates input files for OptumG2, which is a finite element limit analysis (FELA) solver (see next section for more details). The results of preprocessing geometry of cross-sections are presented in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 for Skull Cave and Valentine Cave, respectively.

Fig. 1. (a) Orthographic view of down sampled and trimmed point cloud for Skull Cave, (b) cross-sections generated in CloudCompare for Skull Cave.

Fig. 2. (a) Orthographic view of down sampled and trimmed point cloud for Valentine Cave, (b) cross-sections generated in CloudCompare for Valentine Cave.

4. Methods

4.1. Methodology overview

The proposed approach consists of several steps that can also be applied to caves other than those analyzed by us. First, after preparing laser scans (Step 1, Section 3), we generated cross-sections (Step 2), which were then used to construct a numerical model in the OptumG2 software (Step 4), where the cave cross-section was integrated with the surface topography. In Step 4, we incorporated the mechanical parameters of the rock mass (Step 3), resulting in the numerical model. Numerical analyses were conducted as described in Section 4.2 for all cross-sections (Step 5). Finally, the output data is processed to extract the geometric characteristics of collapses, following Sections 4.2 and 4.3. The overview of the workflow is shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Flowchart of the proposed approach.

4.2. Finite element limit analysis (FELA) approach

Stability analyses were performed using the upper bound formulation of limit analysis, which is implemented in the OptumG2 software. This is a highly efficient method for stability assessment that allows for the determination of collapse mechanisms (see, e.g., Krabbenhoft and Lyamin, 2015; Lim et al., 2017; Chwała et al., 2024b). We used in-house MATLAB procedures developed specifically for this study to generate input files for OptumG2, containing the irregular geometries of lava tube cross-sections. Throughout the analysis, we collected gravity multipliers, which describe how many times gravity must be increased to cause collapse. Gravity acceleration is treated as a multiplier load in FELA analyses; therefore, gravity multipliers allow for stability comparisons between cross-sections (the higher the gravity multiplier, the higher the stability). In addition to gravity multipliers, the geometrical

characteristics of the collapsed area are also under investigation. To increase the accuracy (which here means obtaining lower estimates of upper bound of gravity load) and reduce the computation time, we used adaptive mesh refinement with three iterations, which provide denser finite element meshes in the meaningful regions. Most of the analysis have used 2000 FEs in each adaptive mesh step. The assumed boundary conditions are fixed support at the bottom part of the model and horizontal restraint on the sides, allowing for vertical displacements. An example of finite element mesh along with numerical model for selected Skull Cave cross section is shown in Fig. 4. Stability analysis performed by FELA deliver velocity fields that can be interpreted as the velocity field at the initial stage of the collapse. We use velocity field to extract geometry characteristics of the collapsed area. To separate the region in rest from the collapse region, we used a coefficient ε , to scale down the maximum velocity and establish a threshold to distinguish between collapsed and non-collapsed areas in the rock domain. In the study we have used $\varepsilon = 200$.

Fig. 4. Numerical model (left panel) and finite element mesh in the final adaptive mesh refinement stage (right panels).

4.3. Analyzed scenarios

A total of 125 cross-sections created for Skull Cave and 166 cross-sections created for Valentine Cave were analyzed using the upper bound formulation of finite element limit analysis (FELA). The results consist of individual velocity field distributions at the initial phase of the collapse, accompanied by gravity multipliers. As discussed, the gravity multiplier describes how many times Earth's gravitational acceleration should be increased to initiate a collapse. If the gravity multiplier has a value greater than 1.0, it suggests a stable configuration. However, if its value is below 1.0, it indicates an unstable configuration. By comparing the gravity multiplier values obtained for different cross-sections, a useful measure can be derived to determine which cross-section is more stable. This approach is suitable for cases where there is a lack of detailed knowledge about the mechanical parameters of the rock mass, as is the case here. Therefore, we have assumed strength parameter values corresponding to highly eroded rock, based on available visual inspection, photographic documentation, and the fact that both lava tubes were formed more than 12,000 years ago. Most of the analyses were conducted using the following rock mass properties: a rock unit weight of 30 kN/m^3 , cohesion of 0.5 MPa , and a friction angle of 30° . We have also performed comparative analyses for selected cases, which are within the reported ranges of rock mechanical parameters (e.g., Wines and Lilly, 2003; Villeneuve and Heap, 2021). In each such situation, if other parameters were used, they are clearly stated in the figure or result descriptions.

Numerical analyses were performed for two caves and three scenarios of roof geometry and thickness, i.e., actual surface topography delivered via laser scanning, as described in Section 3, constant roof thickness of 1.0 m or 5.0 m . Constant roof thicknesses are used to investigate the impact of irregular cave geometry and the cave's size on the stability (such treatment enables the omission of the effect of variable roof thickness and surface irregular topography). Each scenario is calculated for three sets of rock strength properties, where in each set, the tension cut-off is changed as detailed in Table 1.

Table 1. Names of scenarios considered in numerical stability analysis with number of analyzed cross-sections.

	No tension cut-off		Tension cut-off 300 kPa		Tension cut-off 100 kPa	
	Skull	Valentine	Skull	Valentine	Skull	Valentine
Actual surface topography	S1 125 cross-sections	V1 161 cross-section	S4 125 cross-sections	V4 161 cross-section	S7 125 cross-sections	V7 161 cross-section
Constant roof thickness 1 m	S2 125 cross-sections	V2 166 cross-section	S5 125 cross-sections	V5 166 cross-section	S8 125 cross-sections	V8 166 cross-section
Constant roof thickness 5 m	S3 125 cross-sections	V3 166 cross-section	S6 125 cross-sections	V6 166 cross-section	S9 125 cross-sections	V9 166 cross-section

5. Results

First, we present the results obtained for Skull Cave and Valentine Cave separately in Sections 5.1 and 5.2, respectively. Then, in Section 5.3, we compare them with each other and discuss them in detail in Section 5.4.

5.1. Skull cave

Gravity multipliers resulting from the upper bound limit analysis along the Skull Cave path are shown in Fig. 5, where three roof scenarios and a tension cut-off of 300 kPa are considered (see cases S4, S5, and S6 in Table 1, for scenarios with tension cut-off of 100 kPa see Fig. S1 in the Supporting Information). A strong correlation between the gravity multipliers for the three scenarios is observed. The results show significant fluctuations in the gravity multiplier over a relatively short cave length of 125 meters. It should be emphasized that, in the case of a constant roof thickness, the influence of variable roof thickness is eliminated, leaving two main factors responsible for these fluctuations: the irregular geometry of the cross-section and the varying size of the cross-section itself. Notably, despite the visible correlation between different scenarios of the rock roof geometry, there are areas where the differences between the constant 1m and 5m roof are minimal, as well as areas where they increase by over 100%. This effect is illustrated in Fig. 6, which shows the percentage differences between the gravity multipliers obtained for the three scenarios.

Fig. 5. Skull Cave stability along its path for three rock roof scenarios with a tension cut-off of 300 kPa.

Surprisingly, for some cross-sections, the differences in gravity multipliers are negligible, as seen, for example, in the region near cross-section no. 48. However, some cross-sections show significant differences in gravity multipliers, such as those near cross-section no. 67. This observation indicates that there are cross-sections where changing the roof thickness does not affect stability (expressed by the gravity multiplier), while for others, stability can vary significantly. This suggests that irregular geometries impact failure mechanisms in a non-trivial manner.

Fig.6. Percentage differences between gravity multipliers obtained for three scenarios, i.e., S4, S5, and S6 for Skull cave.

To investigate the reasons for this observation, the collapse areas corresponding to cross-section no. 48 and cross-section no. 67 are plotted in Fig. 7. The scale of the total displacement (total displacement represents the velocity field resulting from the FELA model solution) is intentionally saturated to highlight the entire collapsing area in red. The collapse shapes found are similar for the two cross-sections and for a variety of roof thickness geometries. However, a deeper analysis of shear dissipation and velocity field orientations provides further insights into the collapse mechanism.

Fig. 7. Total displacement maps obtained for three roof thickness scenarios for cross sections no. 48 (three top panels) and cross-sections no. 67 (three bottom panels).

Shear dissipation and the interpretation of velocity vector orientations are shown in Fig. 8 for the four left panels from Fig. 7 (these are cases with constant roof thickness). A change in the collapse mechanism is observed with increasing roof thickness. For cross-section no. 48, the mechanism with a 1 m roof thickness shows a roof breach in the central part. However, increasing the roof thickness to 5 m changes the collapse mechanism to a one-sided failure, with a roof breach on the right side near the cave wall. Interestingly, for this cave geometry, the two mechanisms provide practically the same stability levels (the 5 m roof case is negligibly more stable). For cross-section no. 67, a different collapse is observed. The symmetrical collapse with a roof breach in the central part for a 1 m roof thickness changes to an inverted cone geometry collapse, which moves practically downward and results in a significant increase in stability (over 100%).

Fig. 8. Shear dissipation (energy dissipation) for two constant roof scenarios (1m and 5 m) with added displacement visualization and arrows indicating the collapse mechanism. The scale of shear dissipation is different for each figure and is saturated for better visibility. The hulls of the shear dissipation are the displacement maps shown in four left panels in Fig. 7.

5.2. Valentine cave

The same three roof thickness scenarios as in Skull Cave are considered for Valentine Cave. The resulting gravity multipliers, shown in Fig. 9 (for scenarios with tension cut-off of 100 kPa see Fig. S2 in the Supporting Information), exhibit greater differences along the cave path than those obtained for Skull Cave. These differences are due to two factors: first, in cross-sections 59, 96-109, and 151-161, the cave contains two separate smaller voids, causing a sudden increase in stability, as seen in Fig. 9. The second factor is the greater variation in cave dimensions compared to Skull Cave. Overall, Valentine Cave has smaller dimensions and more oblique shapes, resulting in greater stability.

Fig. 9. Valentine Cave stability along its path for three rock roof scenarios with a tension cut-off of 300 kPa.

The percentage differences in gravity multipliers for Valentine cave are shown in Fig. 10. Similarly like in the case of Skull cave, there are regions for which significant differences in stability are observed for different roof thicknesses, such as cross-section no. 20 or no. 139, and regions where different roof thickness has very limited impact on stability, such as cross section no. 32 or no. 104. When analyzing the collapse mechanisms for these cross-sections it is observed, that for cross-section no. 20 a collapse with roof breach in the central part is obtained for roof thickness 1m, which transits to inverted cone collapse when roof thickness increases to 5 m. However, in the case of cross-section no. 32 qualitatively the same collapse occurs for roof thicknesses 1 m and 5 m and result in almost the same gravity multiplier. Such scenario is observed because relatively small size of the cave in this location in relation to roof thickness and the close to circular shape of the upper roof geometry. Shear dissipation with indication of collapse mechanism is presented for these two cross-sections in Fig. 11.

Fig. 10. Percentage differences between gravity multipliers obtained for three scenarios, i.e., V4, V5, and V6 for Valentine cave.

Fig. 11. Shear dissipation (energy dissipation) for two constant roof scenarios (1m and 5 m) with added displacement visualization and arrows indicating the collapse mechanism. Note, that due to the displacement visualization, the apparent cross-section geometry is distorted. The scale of shear dissipation is different for each figure and is saturated for better visibility.

Cross-section no. 104 is in the area where two voids are present. The analysis of collapse mechanisms for this case is shown in Fig. 12, where the mutual interference of the two voids also affects stability. The left panel clearly demonstrates the significance of cross-sectional geometry. Despite the greater width of the left cave and the smaller thickness of the roof, the right cave exhibits lower stability, as indicated by the observed collapse mechanism with inverted cone geometry. Interestingly, for this particular case, increasing the roof thickness from 1 m to 5 m (right panel in Fig. 12) results in a slight decrease in stability of the cave system, caused by collapse mechanisms involving both caves.

Fig. 12. Shear dissipation (energy dissipation) for two constant roof scenarios (1m and 5 m) with added arrows indicating the collapse mechanism. The scale of shear dissipation is different for each figure and is saturated for better visibility.

5.3. Skull and Valentine Caves comparative analysis.

The cross-sections of the two caves vary significantly along their paths and also demonstrate differences between both caves. Overall, Valentine Cave is smoother and smaller in diameter than Skull cave. . For a quantitative comparison of collapse characteristics for both caves, we have plotted each cross-section as a point on the gravity multiplier–collapse area plane, as shown in Fig. 13. Additionally, two tension cut-off scenarios were considered: 300 kPa for the three top panels and 100 kPa for the three bottom panels. Based on the resulting points in Fig. 13, it can be observed that the cross-sections for both caves are located in different regions. Valentine Cave is characterized by smaller collapse areas and greater stability (greater gravity multipliers) compared to Skull Cave. One interesting feature that further distinguishes the two caves is the trend in collapse area as a function of the gravity multiplier. Interestingly, this trend is opposite for the two caves. In the case of Skull Cave, the collapse surface area increases with increasing gravity multiplier, whereas for Valentine Cave, the collapse surface area decreases as the gravity multiplier increases. Other observations can be made based on Fig. 13, such as greater stability on average with thicker rock roofs, visible for both tension cut-off scenarios, or smaller collapse areas observed for lower rock tensile strength (lower tension cut-off values). The latter effect is not uniform across all scenarios – it is relatively weak for a 1 m roof thickness and clearly visible for a 5 m roof thickness, especially in the case of Valentine Cave. This observation was earlier reported by Chwała et al. (2024a), noting that the tension cut-off value does not significantly affect collapse geometries for relatively thin roofs (note that this relation differs between Skull and Valentine caves due to the different average sizes of the two caves).

Fig. 13. Collapse areas versus gravity multipliers for different rock roof scenarios. The three top panels correspond to a tension cut-off of 300 kPa, while the three bottom panels correspond to a tension cut-off of 100 kPa.

Due to the caves' irregular shapes, each cross-section has a different width, which strongly affects stability. To reduce this effect, we normalized the collapse areas presented in Fig. 13 by dividing them by the cave width for each cross-section. Therefore, as a result of this normalization, qualitative changes in the point distributions are observed, as shown in Fig. 14. After normalization, the trend in collapse area as a function of the gravity multiplier remains similar for Skull Cave but changes for Valentine Cave, where no increase in normalized collapse area is observed with decreasing gravity multiplier, as seen in the non-normalized data presented in Fig. 13. This observation indicates that smaller gravity multipliers were obtained for greater sections of Valentine Cave (the effect was removed after normalization with respect to cave width). Interestingly, this was not observed for Skull Cave, and in the following sections, we will attempt to answer the question of why this surprising situation occurs?

Fig. 14. Normalized collapse areas versus gravity multipliers for different rock roof scenarios. Three top panels are for tension cut-off of 300 kPa, while the three bottom panels are for tension cut-off of 100 kPa.

Fig. 15. Normalized collapse areas versus gravity multipliers for different rock roof scenarios. The figure contains Fig. 14 with added names and locations of the considered cross-sections. Three top panels are for tension cut-off of 300 kPa, while the three bottom panels are for tension cut-off of 100 kPa.

In the following paragraph, we will present comparisons of collapse areas obtained for selected cross-sections. For clarity, Fig. 15 uses Fig. 14 with the added names of the considered cross-sections. As noted earlier, changing the tension cut-off from 300 kPa to 100 kPa did not significantly affect the collapse areas or the stability of Skull Cave. To investigate the possible reasons, Fig. 16 shows three selected cross-sections (whose locations are indicated in Fig. 15 as A, B, and C). Despite the fact that all three cross-sections have the same minimum roof thickness of 5 m, they exhibit different stability (stability increases from A to C), which is mostly due to the smaller width of the cave (as seen in case C) and different roof shapes. Note that cases A and B have almost the same width (22.33 m and 22.18 m, for A and B, respectively, with a ratio of 1.007); however, the obtained gravity multipliers are significantly different (2.382 and 3.502 for A and B, respectively, with a ratio of 1.47). It is observed that the collapse areas are not affected by the smaller tension cut-off value (please compare the top and bottom panels in Fig. 16). Regarding the gravity multipliers, slightly lower values are obtained for the smaller tension cut-off value. The mild impact of using a tension cut-off of 100 kPa instead of 300 kPa is also visible in the mean values of gravity multipliers and normalized collapse areas, which change only slightly for Skull Cave between the top and bottom panels in Fig. 13 or Fig. 14.

Fig. 16. Collapse areas for three Skull cave cross section and two tension cut-off scenarios (300 kPa for top panels and 100 kPa for bottom panels). Gravity multipliers and normalized collapse areas for these cross-sections are provided in Fig. 15.

A noticeably different situation is observed for Valentine Cave, where reducing the tension cut-off causes a significant decrease in collapse area. Additionally, for a tension cut-off of 100 kPa and a roof thickness of 5 m, two horizontally extended groups of points are observed, suggesting the existence of two different collapse mechanisms, each characterized by different collapse areas. For detailed examination, three points are selected from both groups (upper group: D, F, H; bottom group: E, G, I, see the central bottom panel in Fig. 15). The collapse geometries obtained for the upper group, compared with the scenario of a tension cut-off of 300 kPa, are shown in Fig. 17. In this case, slightly smaller collapse areas are obtained for a tension cut-off of 100 kPa (top panels in Fig. 17).

Fig. 17. Collapse area comparison for cross-sections D, F, and H from Fig. 15 for Valentine cave and two tension cut-off scenarios.

A different situation is observed for the cross-sections in the bottom group (see E, G, and I in Fig. 15), where entirely different collapse mechanisms occur between the two tension cut-off scenarios, as shown in Fig. 18. According to the earlier definition, local collapses – those that do not extend toward the surface – are obtained for smaller tension cut-off values. This explains the significant difference in collapse areas between the two groups. The examples in Figs. 17 and 18 allow us to explore what determines why some cross-sections experience local collapses when the tensile strength of the rock is reduced, while others do not. In general, the answer to this question is not straightforward. However, supported by earlier results obtained for artificially generated cross-sections (Chwała et al. 2024a), it can be stated that the tension cut-off value primarily affects cross-sections with a thick rock roof and a non-rounded roof shape. In particular, overhanging rock sections are highly susceptible to local collapses when the tension cut-off value is reduced. Such characteristics can be observed in the cross-sections shown in Fig. 18. Cross-section E features a distinct overhang that triggers a local collapse at a tension cut-off of 100 kPa. In cross-sections G and I, although the upper part of the roof is rounded, the relatively thick rock layer compared to the small width of the cave is another factor contributing to the potential for local collapses. In contrast, for cross-sections D, F, and H (shown in Fig. 17), these effects are not strong enough. Despite reducing the tension cut-off to 100 kPa, the collapse areas remain very similar and still reach the ground surface. Cross-section D is particularly noteworthy because, despite its relatively thin roof compared to the cave width, no local collapse is observed. On the other hand, in cross-section H, despite the relatively thick roof (due to the cave's small width), the collapse still reaches the surface. This can be explained by the nearly circular geometry of the upper part of the roof, which helps prevent the formation of local collapses. It is expected that further reducing the tension cut-off will lead to local collapses in cross-sections D, F, and H as well, a topic that will be discussed in more detail in the Discussion section.

Fig. 18. Collapse area comparison for cross-sections E, G, and I from Fig. 15 for Valentine cave and two tension cut-off scenarios.

Fig. 19. Collapse area comparison for cross-sections A, B, and C from Fig. 11 for Skull cave, tension cut-off 100 kPa and two roof thicknesses.

The surface area of collapses naturally decreases with the reduction of roof thickness, but the horizontal extent of the collapse also becomes smaller. As shown in Fig. 19, for roofs with a thickness of 1 meter, rock overhangs may form, and in many cases, the collapse does not span the full width of the cave. Additionally, the actual surface topography may influence the nature of collapses, as illustrated in Figs. 13 and 14. Three of the previously analyzed cross-sections (G, F, and H) of Valentine Cave are presented in Fig. 20, where the actual surface topography has been taken into account.

Fig. 20. Collapse area comparison for cross-sections G, F, and H from Fig. 11 for Valentine cave, tension cut-off 300 kPa and actual surface topography.

5.4. Discussion

Sections with the lowest stability correspond to areas where the multiplier reaches its minimum value. However, this analysis assumes uniform rock properties, whereas natural variability is expected – such as, on average, improved rock quality in regions with a thicker roof, local weakness due to fractures and vesicular zones. This factor remains uncertain and is not considered in the study. Observations from terrestrial lava tubes suggest that stability fluctuations should also be anticipated in potential lunar caves, highlighting the importance of this approach in selecting suitable sites for future missions and exploration. In the following subsections, we discuss various effects influencing the obtained results, supporting our analysis with additional examinations.

5.4.1. Comparison with earlier results

Fig. 21. Normalized collapse widths versus gravity multipliers for different rock roof scenarios. Three top panels are obtained for tension cut-off 300 kPa, three bottom panels are obtained for tension cut-off 100 kPa. Normalization is done individually for each cross-section by cave width.

Chwała et al. (2024a) proposed normalized collapse width, defined as the ratio of collapse width to cave width, to facilitate comparisons of cave collapse sizes, especially convenient in scenarios with varying cave widths. Since this study is the first to consider irregular geometry of natural cave in stability analyses, we present the results in this convention, as shown in Fig. 21, where the normalized collapse width is plotted on the horizontal axis. A clear difference is observed between Skull Cave and Valentine Cave. In the latter, the scatter of results is significantly larger on the gravity multiplier axis due to the cave's highly variable size. However, in terms of normalized collapse width, the scatter is similar to that in Skull Cave, with generally larger values for Valentine Cave – except for the case with a 5 m roof thickness and a tension cut-off of 100 kPa. This exception results from a significant number of local collapses, as discussed earlier (e.g., Fig. 18). Valentine Cave also exhibits isolated cross-sections with exceptionally large collapse sizes, not observed in previous studies (Chwała et al., 2024a). These result from two adjacent cave tunnels, where collapse mechanisms involve both, as illustrated for one cross-section in Fig. 12. In contrast, Skull Cave is more homogeneous in size, with an average roof thickness-to-half-width ratio consistent with previous analyses. For a 5 m roof thickness, this ratio is 0.46 (5 m / (20.8 m/2)), close to the 0.533 ratio for a homogeneous roof considered in Chwała et al. (2024b), where normalized collapse widths ranged from 0.8 to 1.2, with a mean slightly above 1. As seen in the middle panels of Fig. 21, most collapses fall within this range, with a similar mean. Chwała et al. (2024b) also reported significantly larger reductions in rock tensile strength, leading to local collapses. This was not observed here due to the proportionally smaller reduction in tension cut-off. The results for Skull Cave with a 1 m roof thickness, where the thickness-to-half-width ratio is 0.096, align with those in Chwała et al. (2024a), where a ratio of 0.125 yielded normalized collapse widths from 0.5 to 1.2, with mean value around 0.75-0.8. This matches the values obtained for Skull Cave with a 1 m roof thickness (see the two left panels in Fig. 21).

5.4.2. Tension cut-off influence

Tension cut-off, discussed in the results section, is further examined here through the collapse areas of two selected cross-sections of Valentine Cave, i.e., D and H. These sections result in collapses extending to the surface for a tension cut-off of 100 kPa (see Fig. 17). As discussed there, local collapses would occur if the rock tensile strength were further reduced. Indeed, such collapses are observed in Fig. 22, where tension cut-off values of 50 kPa and 25 kPa were assumed. The nearly circular shape of cross-section H is particularly resistant to local collapses, so a significant reduction in rock tensile strength was needed to trigger such a collapse (see the bottom-right panel in Fig. 22). The tension cut-off can be interpreted as a result of fractures and the degree of degradation of intact rock. For highly degraded rocks, this value can be very small, approaching zero, making the representation of rock mass strength on a macro scale more realistic. The occurrence of localized collapses with small volumes can be associated with local rockfalls, as observed in Skull Cave, where rock debris accumulates on the cave floor.

Fig. 22. Collapse areas obtained for cross-sections D and H of Valentine cave with reduced tensile strength of rock. Compare with Fig. 17.

5.4.3. Influence of finite element mesh density

As the aim of this paper is to investigate potential collapse characteristics for irregular cave shapes, we used the upper bounds of the limit load to determine gravity multipliers. Plasticity theory allows for solving the lower bound formulation, which, together with the upper bound, provides constraints on the limit load. Practically, the average value can be assumed as the limit load, with an accuracy given by half of the range between the lower and upper bounds. Both estimates converge to the limit load as the number of finite elements used to create the mesh increases. Adaptive meshing is employed here to reduce the required number of finite elements and ensure satisfactory accuracy. To illustrate these effects, Fig. 23 shows the dependence of gravity multipliers and normalized collapse width on the finite element mesh for two selected cross-sections: cross-section A for Skull Cave with a tension cut-off of 300 kPa, and cross-section G for Valentine Cave with a tension cut-off of 100 kPa. The results, presented in Fig. 23, investigate a range of finite element counts from 500 to 16,000, with three adaptive mesh iterations. Thanks to the three adaptive steps, the number of finite elements can be significantly reduced compared to a regular mesh assumption. This is particularly advantageous in scenarios like this, where the points defining the irregular shape are not evenly spaced. As observed in earlier studies using FELA

(Krabbenhoft et al., 2015), the gravity multipliers obtained for upper and lower bound assessments converge quickly. The percentage difference between 2,000 FEs used in this study and 16,000 FEs is 2.1% for cross-section A and 2.6% for cross-section G. Additionally, as shown in the right panel of Fig. 23, the number of finite elements does not affect the cave width – a few percent difference in this case can be ignored from the perspective of this study’s objectives.

Fig. 23. Impact of number of finite element on convergence of gravity multipliers obtained by upper and lower bound limit analysis (left panel) and identified cave width for cross-section A of Skull cave and G of Valentine cave.

However, larger differences are observed in the collapse area for scenarios where local collapses are present, such as cross-section G for a tension cut-off of 100 kPa in Fig. 18. To demonstrate the impact of this effect, the scenario most prone to it – Valentine Cave with a roof thickness of 5 m and a tension cut-off (scenario V9 in Table 1) – was analyzed using twice the number of finite elements. For comparison, the Skull Cave scenario with a roof thickness of 5 m and a tension cut-off of 300 kPa (S5) was also analyzed in the same manner. The results are presented in Fig. 24, where negligible differences in gravity multipliers and the identified normalized collapse width were observed. In the case of the collapse area, a noticeable difference between the two mesh densities was observed for the Valentine Cave scenario with a roof thickness of 5 m and a tension cut-off of 100 kPa (which is more prone to this effect as indicated earlier). It is worth noting that the identified collapse geometries and mechanisms are the same in both cases; however, denser meshes result in larger collapse areas due to the greater vertical extent of the collapse (note that the collapse width is not affected by mesh density, see Fig. 23 and Fig. 24). An example of a collapse for the two cross-sections investigated in Fig. 23 is shown in the Supporting Information in Fig. S3.

Fig. 24. Comparison of gravity multipliers vs. normalized collapse width and collapse area obtained for 2000 (blue) and 4000 (red) finite elements in three adaptive mesh iterations for scenario V9 (Valentine Cave) and S5 (Skull cave).

5.4.4. Effects of friction angle, cohesion and bulk density

The previous sections detailed the impact of irregular cave geometry, rock roof thickness, and rock tensile strength on stability and collapses. Here, we examine another parameter, the internal friction angle, which affects the shape of collapses. In the performed analyses, friction angle was assumed to be at a relatively low level of 30° . This assumption was justified by the expected significant degradation of the rock mass in thin rock roofs exposed to atmospheric conditions and is within the lowest reported range of this parameter for volcanic rock (e.g., Villeneuve and Heap, 2021). The internal friction angle naturally influences stability assessment, with higher values increasing stability (higher gravity multipliers). Simultaneously, it affects the collapse shape, as shown in Fig. 25, where the inclination of the failure surface can be approximated by the internal friction angle, especially when a uniformly inclined collapse surface forms. This suggests that a higher internal friction angle results in slightly smaller collapse surfaces and increases the likelihood of larger rock overhangs when the collapse reaches the ground surface.

Fig. 25. Friction angle influence on collapse areas for Skull cave cross-section A and Valentine cross-section G.

In this study, we do not analyze the impact of cohesion and bulk density, as their influence is linear for a given cross-section. An increase in cohesion proportionally increases the gravity multiplier, while a decrease in bulk density has the same effect (this holds under no tension cut-off or when cohesion and tension cut-off are proportionally related). However, both factors significantly affect cave stability. Therefore, in cases requiring precise stability estimation, these parameters should be thoroughly examined. From the perspective of our research, it was crucial that neither parameter affects collapse geometry. This means that the results presented in this study regarding collapse geometry remain unchanged if the cohesion value is modified, provided that the tension cut-off value is adjusted proportionally if applicable. This applies only to a homogeneous rock layer – consideration of layering in the roof may influence collapse shapes, as demonstrated in a recent study on the stability of potential lunar lava tubes under layering in lunar basalts (Chwała et al. 2024b).

5.4.5. The impact of two dimensional analyses

The presented methodology is based on two-dimensional (2D) analyses, which are commonly used in tunnel-related problems and other linear structures with a constant cross-section along their length. However, incorporating irregularities in cave shape and terrain surface, as done in this study, can influence stability estimates and failure geometries compared to three-dimensional (3D) analysis. In general, 2D analyses may lead to greater variability in results, as stability is assessed locally, whereas 3D analyses introduce some degree of averaging. For example, based on Figs. 5 and 9, areas most prone to collapse can be identified where gravity multipliers are lowest. In particular, collapses are more likely in regions where multiple neighboring cross-sections exhibit low stability. On the other hand, if a single cross-section shows low stability while being surrounded by stable sections, it suggests that a collapse is less likely due to the averaging effect expected in three dimensions. This effect will be explored in future studies by the authors. Nevertheless, we believe that conducting stability analyses of lava tubes in two dimensions provides several advantages when using limit analysis methods to determine the geometry of potential collapses. These advantages are outlined below:

- 1) Two-dimensional analyses, as shown in Figs. 5 and 9, allow for a continuous assessment of cave roof stability, enabling the identification of more and less stable regions, as well as the analysis of collapse sizes. The FELA method optimizes the velocity field, meaning it identifies a single collapse mechanism (with the lowest stability) for a given model. This implies that modeling the entire cave section in 3D would yield one collapse mechanism and a single stability value – preventing conclusions about other parts of the cave. A possible workaround is to perform 3D

analyses for individual cave sections, but this approach is conceptually complex and time-consuming, making it significantly more challenging.

- 2) Performing 3D analyses is relatively complex, especially when accounting for the irregular geometry of caves, as we aimed to do. Additionally, achieving sufficient accuracy requires significantly more finite elements than 2D analyses. Consequently, the computation time for a 3D problem can be much longer than that for even hundreds of 2D cross-sections, which, as demonstrated in bullet point 1, provide a comprehensive view of stability and its variations along the cave's path.
- 3) The computational efficiency of FELA in 2D allows for the consideration of numerous variants, even with a large number of cross-sections, as demonstrated in this study. This enables the estimation of uncertainties in the mechanical parameters of the rocks and allows such analyses to be conducted within a reasonable timeframe.

6. Summary and conclusions

The paper presents an approach for assessing the stability of lava tubes, including their irregular shapes. The cross-sections used in the numerical analyses are generated from laser scans of cave interiors. The methodology takes advantage of finite element limit analysis, which offers unique insights into collapse geometries. This approach was used to analyze two lava tubes, Skull Cave and Valentine Cave, marking the first comprehensive analysis of cave stability under irregular shapes known to the authors. Specifically, the study allows us to draw several conclusions about the influence of natural cave geometry irregularities on stability and collapse geometries:

- 1) It has been shown that areas with higher and lower stability overlap when different values of rock roof thickness are considered. Additionally, overlap is also observed for the actual surface topography, indicating that individual cross-section characteristics, such as size and irregular shape, significantly impact stability and should not be ignored in stability analysis.
- 2) Overall, for different tension cut-off levels, the overlap of areas where cross-sections are more or less stable is also maintained. This further highlights the importance of accurately reproducing the irregular geometry of caves in numerical modeling.
- 3) Through the analysis of cross-sections from Skull and Valentine Caves, we identified sections where changes in rock roof thickness had little impact on stability, as well as sections where such changes caused significant stability differences. These differences were due to changes in the collapse mechanism, which can only be identified through individual cross-section analysis.
- 4) Local collapses (collapses that do not reach the surface) become more frequent with smaller tension cut-off values. Their occurrence also depends on the rock roof thickness (the thicker the roof, the more frequent the collapses) and the cross-section geometry. Roofs with overhangs and irregularities are particularly prone to local instability, while rounded roofs with shapes close to a circular cross-section are the most stable.
- 5) In this study, we primarily focused on analyzing single caves. However, the results from a section of a double cave conduit indicate that changes in roof height can shift the collapse mechanism from affecting a single cave to involving both caves. These examples also highlight the importance of cross-section geometry. For instance, in Fig. 12, a collapse occurred in a cave with a thicker roof and narrower width – parameters typically associated with greater stability. Such non-trivial observations arise directly from the shapes of the cross-sections.
- 6) This study is the first to comprehensively analyze the stability and collapse geometry of terrestrial lava tubes. Although the statistical sample is relatively small compared to recent studies on artificially generated irregular cross-sections (Chwała et al., 2024a,b), it is the first numerical analysis to confirm the significant impact of irregular cross-section geometries on stability based on real data. Moreover, the obtained distributions of characteristics, such as normalized cave width, fall within previously reported ranges.

The presented methodology can be applied to other lava tubes and caves of different origins, provided their shapes are approximately linear or their path curvature radii are significantly larger than the dimensions of their cross-sections (this limitation arises from the use of two-dimensional analysis). In areas with high curvature, an axisymmetric approach could be considered. The authors are open to collaboration with teams that have access to laser scans of caves. Future plans include expanding the analyses to incorporate 3D models and statistical processing of cross-section shapes, which will help optimize the process and further improve understanding of collapse mechanisms and risk assessment in lava tubes. In the domain of future analyses, there is also the situation where a new lava flow occurs exclusively on the surface, it is expected that it would initially negatively affect the stability of the cave, as the rock roof would be subjected to additional loading until the lava solidifies. In future analyses, this effect could be modeled by incorporating surface loading. Once the lava solidifies, an increase in stability could be expected, although this would depend on the degree of bonding between the old and new layers. This phenomenon is likely similar to what has been observed on the walls of Mare Tranquillitatis Pit on the Moon (Robinson et al., 2012). The presented approach can also be used as part of the candidate selection process for future lunar cave exploration missions (e.g., Titus et al., 2021).

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Data Availability Statement

Numerical models were analysed using OptumG2 (<https://optumce.com/>).

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